

ROLE OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *There are great opportunities for theoretical and practical independent education of future teachers in higher education institutions. However, in many cases, the issue of formation of self-learning skills and qualifications of pedagogues in the educational process is not considered as an actual pedagogical problem. This article describes a modern approach to the analysis and development of the content of independent education.*

Keywords: *independent education, systematic, consistency, differentiation, professional competence, cognitive, pedagogical problem, individual method, talent.*

Currently, improving the professional competence of future teachers in the process of independent education based on the gradual clarification of the principles of systematicity, consistency, differentiation and individualization, organizational-structural, motivational, cognitive, active, reflexive components of teaching is recognized as a more urgent problem. It is known that the development of professional competence of future teachers is formed as a pedagogical mechanism based on the priority of social identification in subject-subject relations. In turn, it is important to educate a person who has a personal opinion and can make independent decisions, who can listen to the opinions of others and draw conclusions taking them into account. Today's innovations and economic changes taking place in society require appropriate design and standardization of the content of the educational system. The uniqueness of independent education at all levels (stages) of the continuing education system is that it is fundamentally different from the forms, tools, and methods of teaching in modern education.

Development of creative abilities of pedagogues-teachers, strengthening of their demands for knowledge, training of potential pedagogues capable of solving the given problem through the formation of independent thinking skills is one of the important tasks facing the educational system specialized in retraining and upgrading the skills of field workers. The current modern direction of education is that the staff being trained in the general qualification requirements set for the level of teacher training in the state requirements should be able to independently make decisions related to their field, have competitive professional training, organize their creativity on a scientific basis, and independently improve their knowledge, skills, experience and qualifications. Independent education occupies a special place in the training of personnel with such abilities in school education.

Modern methods, forms and tools, technologies, problem-based teaching and independent education play an important role in improving the quality and efficiency of education. This requires conducting serious scientific research on the development of the content of the independent education of future teachers and the improvement of the methods of its organization and implementation in higher education organizations.

There are great opportunities for future teachers to get theoretical and practical independent education in higher education institutions. However, in many cases, in the process of education,

the issue of formation of independent learning skills and competencies of students is not considered as an urgent pedagogical problem, the analysis and development of the content of independent education is not approached from a modern point of view, and sufficient attention is not paid to the use of its effective methods, forms and tools. Other similar issues indicate the existence of a number of pedagogical problems in the organization, implementation, and control of independent education of future teachers in personnel training in institutions specialized in training future teachers.

There is a need to study these issues from a scientific-pedagogical perspective, taking into account the necessity for educators to engage in independent learning within the educational process. It is essential to create adequate conditions for them to acquire independent knowledge. Currently, the professional-pedagogical preparation of teachers to organize, implement, and monitor independent education does not meet the required standards. There is an insufficient development of knowledge, skills, and qualifications among educators regarding independent learning and the organization of students' independent education. As a result of the lack of educational and methodical literature, recommendations, developments, guidelines, instructions related to implementation and control, some of the personnel in teacher training institutes have not fully formed the skills to make independent decisions and defend their point of view, which shows the extreme urgency of these issues.

New modern forms of education exist in combination with traditional forms, which allows to model real situations of professional activity in educational activities, in which the gap between education and training processes is eliminated, and professional competence corresponding to the modern specialist model is formed. The main place in the formation of innovative competence is occupied by the independent work of pedagogues. This can be achieved by teaching pedagogues to independently solve problematic assignments and tasks in the educational process. Based on this general goal, independent education accustoms teachers to fully use their intellectual powers, to find the necessary knowledge, and to apply it to their practical activities in any situation. In a word, it prepares to work as a full-fledged, competitive specialist in social life and in the development process. The teacher is looking for ways and methods, individual methods and tools of teaching that are convenient for him and the learner, and improve them. Learning materials specified in the curriculum, program and textbooks are mastered. It is taught to use in practical activities, to achieve guaranteed results. In this process, paying attention to the future teacher's independent activity as much as possible will give a positive result.

In independent education in professional work, the pedagogue is able to search for knowledge related to his specialty outside the curriculum and textbooks, and enrich it further by conducting experiments. This, in turn, motivates the formation of enterprising and creative personnel. The main thing is to create a favorable innovative environment in the school. Self-directed learning creates positive competition among educators. Students, following the example of each other, direct their minds, energy, and time to engage in useful activities. Certain aspects of the student's talent are revealed by preparing for various competitions, participating in science olympiads and striving to win, and participating in scientific and creative exhibitions.

Independent education also has a positive effect on the development of young people as individuals. It stabilizes character traits, in particular, strengthens willpower, improves self-control. They are used to not being indifferent to things and events in the environment, to be able to evaluate them correctly, to express and prove their independent opinions. As a result of creating

a separate creative environment, not only the exchange of information and experience on the pedagogical problem takes place, but due to the creation of a separate co-creative environment, openness to new ideas is achieved, which later serves as a basis for the application of innovative competence.

Competence itself implies that future teachers have a broad general worldview and a high level of culture, the ability to develop their knowledge in practice, knowledge of social and psychological-pedagogical research methods, and the necessary set of pedagogical and management skills. In other words, competence is determined by the presence of professional knowledge and skills, as well as the ability to apply and improve them in practical activities, and innovative competence is the sum of personal capabilities of a specialist, his ability to creatively apply his knowledge and experience in practical activities.

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